

Child Welfare Institution: Examining Faith-Based Organizations In Managing Muhammadiyah Child Welfare Institution

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Abstract

This research aims to identify and analyze the functioning of child social welfare institutions (LKSA), especially faith-based ones (FBO), with a focus on the recruitment process, human resource management, childcare patterns, and the differences between Muhammadiyah and Government child welfare institutions. Through a qualitative descriptive study using case study techniques, interviews, and focus group sessions, this research explores recruitment practices and human resource management in Muhammadiyah FBOs. The results showed that LKSA Muhammadiyah has a standard childcare service that is based on Islamic values, with three care program approaches that include family compensation, family care, and shelter for abandoned children. The recruitment process at LKSA Muhammadiyah involves a system of regeneration, relations, internships, and volunteering, which aims to ensure the sustainability of Muhammadiyah values in the management of the institution. A comparison between recruitment systems in the government and Muhammadiyah sectors shows differences in priorities, procedures, and practices applied. This research provides insights into the importance of religious values in the management of LKSA as well as practical implications for the development of human resource management policies and practices in child social welfare institutions.

Keywords: Child Social Welfare Institution, Human Resource Management, Childcare, Service Quality

1. INTRODUCTION

Of Indonesia's 2.15 million children, 500,000 do not live with their biological parents for a decent family life (O'Kane & Lubis, 2016). According to Rodriguez et al, (2021), a decent life in the family includes access to basic needs such as adequate food, shelter, education, and health services. In this case, it also includes emotional aspects such as healthy relationships, good communication, and psychological support between family members, in accordance with the opinion of Duflos et al. (2022), (2022). According to Avedissian & Alayan, (2021) According to Avedissian & Alayan, (2021), this shows the importance of conditions that support overall growth and well-being for families, both in terms of physical and emotional. Therefore, it is a joint task for government agencies and *stakeholders* involved in child protection to promote an integrated social welfare system for Indonesian children. Child social welfare agencies (CSOs) within faith-based organizations (FBOs) play an important role in providing care and support for vulnerable children, often guided by the values and principles of their respective religious beliefs. (Bartkowski & Grettenberger, 2018)..

The services of children's social welfare agencies are driven by a volunteer movement based on a commitment to child protection to improve welfare (Rohman et al., 2022). According to Gunawardena & Stich, (2021) to encourage this commitment, a system that designs functions to intervene in child welfare through child social welfare institutions is needed, in the same view Omona, (2019) assesses the need for a stable institution to realize this, but Omona, (2019) underlines that principles are needed in the management of child welfare institutions to achieve child welfare goals. LKSA has been the focus of promotion by *volunteer* movements from religious backgrounds. Faith-based organizations (FBOs) have been active in the health sector for decades, and interest in the role of FBOs in health is growing. For example, in Indonesia, there is a child social welfare agency founded by a faith-based organization, Muhammadiyah, which has been operating since 1932 and is spread across various regions in Indonesia to date. (Anwari et al., 2023)..

In general, child social welfare institutions play a role in child protection, functioning for child character development, and childcare. The Indonesian government firmly ensures that it carries out the law's mandate and provides professional social workers' services. Meanwhile, LKSA Muhammadiyah is also almost the same as other LKSA which are engaged in child protection services, child character development, and childcare patterns. However, the addition of the function of LKSA Muhammadiyah as a religion-based organization adds to the knowledge of religion. (Putri & Sahrul, 2021; Sahrul et al., 2022).. According to Soelton et al, (2023) LKSA needs to make changes to improve services, good quality services show commitment to the presence of a decent life for children. In the child welfare agency system, current policies make agencies responsible only for achieving desired outcomes without considering the impact of individual and social factors that can affect agency performance (Raghavan, 2010). (Raghavan, 2010). According to Gander et al, (2019) to bring about improvements in child welfare agencies, it is important to provide professional support or services for service recipients. This is agreed by Owusu & Frimpong-Manso, (2020) considers that residents of child welfare institutions or people with special needs are likely to lose the social and economic benefits provided by the government if they do not receive excellent services from child social welfare institutions. Therefore, it is very important for child social welfare institutions to have very high service quality standards to support consistent and continuous improvement of organizational performance so that residents of child social welfare institutions have a positive impact on changing children's behavior through care by professionals. (Kleinrahm et al., 2013)..

In recent years, the study of child social welfare institutions has been promoted to look at the quality of services, studies such as human resource development of professional workers (Christiansen & Lorås, 2020; Nurul et al., 2019; Owusu & Frimpong-Manso, 2020; Rohman et al., 2022; Soelton et al., 2023), child welfare agency management (Carnochan et al., 2013; Gunawardena & Stich, 2021; Huggins-Hoyt et al., 2019; Omona, 2019; Samples et al., 2013) and parenting patterns (Berger & Paar, 2017; Gander et al., 2019; Garstka et al., 2012; Kleinrahm et al., 2013; Raghavan, 2010).. Some of these studies have explained the function of LKSA as a child protection institution but there are still few studies that promote the function of LKSA from the recruitment process.

Child welfare organizations in Indonesia are promoted by *volunteer* movements with religious backgrounds. Typically, public and private child welfare agencies are very different (Jayaratne & Faller, 2009). (Jayaratne & Faller, 2009).. This has led to new considerations for child social welfare agencies to collaborate between agencies (Collins-Camargo & McBeaver, 2009). (Collins-Camargo & McBeath, 2017; Spath et al., 2008).. According to Susilowati (2022) government child social welfare agencies need to develop human resources through training. In addition, government children's social welfare institutions lack awareness in child protection due to the low level of knowledge of government LKSA

human resources. (Sumardika, 2022). Meanwhile, Muhammadiyah child welfare institutions have a very good institutional management commitment because they develop religious characters (Gunawan & Syamsudin, 2023). (Gunawan & Syamsudin, 2023)(Gunawan & Syamsudin, 2023), and collaborating with other institutions and developing a framework for managing the institution in order to provide the best childcare patterns (Bunger et al., 2014). (Bunger et al., 2014).

Based on the above description, this research aims to identify and describe the functions of child social welfare institutions (LKSA), especially those that are faith-based, with a focus on the recruitment process. Thus, this research can provide insights and recommendations for government agencies and stakeholders involved in child protection to improve an integrated social welfare system for Indonesian children, with a focus on the role of LKSA.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Child Welfare Institution Performance

Children's social welfare institutions in dealing with problems do not stand alone, requiring the role of cross-sectors, this role answers the need for collaboration in handling welfare problems for children. (Garstka et al., 2012) In the view of Huggins-Hoyt et al, (2019) private agencies perform well in handling child welfare issues. This is supported by a framework by Carnochan et al, (2013) (2013) that private child social welfare agencies manage the agency by planning performance measurement and performance management strategies. Thus, the impact of the performance measurement and performance management strategy framework has a profound influence on the design, implementation and evaluation of child social welfare services at the local level. (Samples et al., 2013).

To ensure service excellence in the context of child social welfare agencies, resource management is essential to improve the quality of these services (Singh Dubey et al., 2022; Stredwick, 2013).. These enhanced skills through resource management are a reflection of the urgent need for quality services provided to children (Hardina, 2002). (Hardina, 2002). Therefore, according to Hargie, (2021) concrete steps are needed to improve skills through the implementation of training programs and the placement of human resources in accordance with the required competencies. This approach not only supports service effectiveness, but also helps secure high quality standards in the child welfare intervention process. Thus, resource management focused on skills development is an important foundation in the effort to improve responsive and quality services in child social welfare institutions.

2.2. Faith-based Organizations (FBO)

Faith-based organizations have varied da'wah movements (Qodir et al., 2022) The movement is based on the way faith-based organizations promote the philanthropy movement. Faith-based organizations in general have the potential to increase the strategic capacity to collaborate, and the religiosity aspect of ministry can be an impetus for collaboration between organizations. (Fu et al., 2020; Sahrul et al., 2022).. FBOs in Islamic countries such as Indonesia are popularized by religious organizations, according to Baidhawiy (2015) the function of philanthropic organizations encourages problem solving. Therefore Clarke & Ware (2015) assume that there is a need for more religious organizations to promote philanthropic movements that pay attention to humanitarian issues. Religious organizations involved in these conditions are based on unstable social, economic, and political conditions because the role of Ngos is to create stable conditions by providing volunteer movements. (Göçmen, 2013).

Broady & Gray (2018) FBOs generally collaborate with governments to address social and economic issues. This method is generally referred to as collaborartive action to reach out to affected communities, or in the view of the FBOs (Fu et al., 2020). (Fu et al., 2020) calls it a corss-sectoral partnership, with the capacity that FBOs have to provide more optimal services because it is based on the non-business movement. Therefore, in the view of Göçmen, (2013) religious organizations are private organizations that can provide better social services, this way answers that FBOs in practice are in accordance with the way religious organizations through modern organizational methods, this is indicated by the form of social services offered by religious organizations. (Sakai, 2012)to address the problems of poverty and social inequality in the community (Clarke & Ware, 2015). (Clarke & Ware, 2015).

2.3. Private good, child welfare, and public services

There are two types of child social welfare institutions: private and public. Both provide social services for children (Jayaratne & Faller, 2009)However, the difference between private and public child social welfare institutions is the segment of services and childcare (Soelton et al., 2023). (Soelton et al., 2023), institution management (Sahrul et al., 2022), competence of professionals (Korpinen & Pösö, 2020).. According to Auerbach et al. (2010) from the above functions of child social welfare institutions, the best child social welfare institutions are driven by competent and qualified human resources in managerial and technical skills in management, care, and services. In the view of Soelton et al. (2023) There are strong relationships in the management of child welfare institutions, such as culture and leadership factors that drive service quality improvement. Thus (Dormer, 2011) there is a need for professional practice in child welfare agencies or child protection agencies, furthermore (Dormer, 2011) argues that institutional factors can influence services.

In the view of Jayaratne & Faller (2009) there are public and private institutions that are concerned with child welfare, and these institutions also guarantee the right to survival by providing employment (Faller et al., 2010). (Faller et al., 2010). By (Huggins-Hoyt et al., 2019) (Huggins-Hoyt et al., 2019) assessed that the services provided by public and private institutions provide mixed results in child protection. Service improvement in child social welfare agencies is based on service standards and performance in the agency (Flaherty et al., 2008). (Flaherty et al., 2008)(Flaherty et al., 2008), thereby promoting social services (Collins-Camargo et al., 2011)..

However, according to Molnar et al, (2020) High-quality child social welfare institutions are also driven by the ability of the institution's managers, Husby et al, (2018) assessed that the quality level of orphanage residents can be developed through trusting relationships, emotional support, and pedagogical approaches to increase children's participation in their interactions with professionals. Therefore, the management of private and public child social welfare institutions is important in caring for children who have different backgrounds. (Brown et al., 2019). One of the main functions of child social welfare institutions is the competence of professionals and the residents of orphanages (Park & Pierce, 2020)Li et al, (2020) argued that considering human resources in child welfare agencies to try to improve the job satisfaction of professionals can have influences such as providing good wages, benefits, and promotion opportunities at the managerial level.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research begins by building assumptions based on research conducted by (Luara Frame, 2003) to look at child welfare institution reform. Through the case study approach used, the research provided a clear illustration of service reform in child welfare

institutions. In several other case studies a qualitative approach was used to confirm the hypotheses and research questions, Smithson & Gibson (2017) did so to confirm the findings of the indepth interviews with the interviewees. This method was chosen to test the focus of the research by looking at the variable findings (Bennett & Elman, 2017). (Bennett & Elman, 2006) In this way, the findings are developed comprehensively by testing the theory used. Qualitative case study (S. Li & Seale, 2007) can be developed with more interesting data comparisons by comparing other case studies.

The data collection process in this research was carried out by conducting observations, focus group discussions and indepth interviews directly with the managers of child social welfare institutions. Data collection was carried out in four child social welfare organizations owned by Muhammadiyah. The process of collecting data through focus group discussions and in-depth interviews is adjusted to the research objectives and research questions, so that this research is designed to answer both clearly as the function of case studies in qualitative research. According to Bennett & Elman (2006) with a more varied number of case studies, the findings in the research will provide a clear picture that can be validated by researchers through strong data. The data sources in the study consisted of four child welfare institutions owned by Muhammadiyah.

Data analysis in this study uses the ATLAS.ti tool, in qualitative research this tool is categorized as Qualitative Data Software Analysis (QDSA). (Paulus et al., 2017) This tool is categorized as Qualitative Data Analysis Software (QDSA) (Paulus et al., 2017), and as a tool commonly used in qualitative research. (Silver & Lewins, 2014). ATLAS.ti functions to synchronize in research between transcripts and audio obtained through focus group discussions and interviews. Kuckartz & Rädiker (2019) QDSA tool can analyze documents such as PDF, Word, TXT, therefore the type of data in the research has been formatted according to how QDSA ATLAS.ti works. The analysis function through QDSA starts with (1) Data type (import data) 2. Data management and usability, 3. Transcription, 4. Qualitative data analysis, 5. Mixed methods, 6. Visualization, 7. Teamwork 8. Report and publish and 9. Analysis.

Figure 1 Research methods chart analysis

Based on the QDSA function described by (Kuckartz & Rädiker, 2019). (Kuckartz & Rädiker, 2019), this research developed a flow chart as a data analysis process. See Figure

1, the process starts with (1) data collection, (2) data interpretation and document interpretation, (3) data coding, (4) analysis of data content, (5) interpretation of findings, and drawing conclusions. Through the QDSA stage, the research data will be processed following the process as shown in Figure 1.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Recruitment System at LKSA Muhammadiyah

LKSA Muhammadiyah has a recruitment model started by the parent organization through the Muhammadiyah Social Welfare Development Assembly through an open recruitment system by conducting open selection by candidates. Recruitment is based on the needs of the LKSA, so that recruitment becomes open to candidates who have the ability in that field. Paik & Navarre-Jackson (2010) Generally, social movements based on volunteerism are seen as movements that care about the environment and community conditions, which are also supported by the organization's social network. Muhammadiyah is an organization with a social network that attracts many volunteers to get involved in it, which is shown in several social activity practices. (Anwari et al., 2023; Baidhaw, 2015; Gunawan & Syamsudin, 2023).

Figure 1. Human Resource Fulfillment Flow

The flowchart figure 1 represents the systematic process of fulfilling human resource needs within an organizational structure. It begins with the identification of human resource requirements, followed by a series of formal steps involving multiple organizational bodies. The process is initiated when a need for personnel arises, prompting the submission of an application to the Lembaga Kesejahteraan Sosial Anak (LKSA). This institution acts as an intermediary body that processes the application and formalizes a proposal letter to be forwarded to the Muhammadiyah Sukajadi Branch Leadership. This structured approach ensures that resource allocation is managed efficiently and follows the proper administrative channels.

From an organizational theory perspective, this process aligns with Max Weber's Bureaucratic Theory, which emphasizes a hierarchical structure and formal procedures in

decision-making. Each step in the flowchart represents a bureaucratic process where requests are reviewed and approved by different levels of authority before action is taken. The involvement of multiple organizations, such as the Muhammadiyah Sukajadi Branch Leadership and the Social Service Assembly, highlights the principle of delegation—a fundamental concept in management where responsibilities are distributed across different entities to ensure accountability and order.

Furthermore, the role of the Social Service Assembly in the process is critical as it acts as a regulatory body that assesses the suitability of the human resource allocation. This aligns with decision-making theories, particularly Herbert Simon's theory of bounded rationality, which suggests that organizations follow a step-by-step, rational decision-making process within the constraints of available information and resources. The structured flow of the process demonstrates a sequential decision-making model, ensuring that approvals are made systematically before final implementation. Such an approach reduces uncertainty and promotes efficiency in resource management.

Finally, the flowchart concludes with the allocation of human resources to LKSA Healthy Babies, indicating the ultimate goal of the process. This outcome aligns with human resource management (HRM) theories, particularly the resource-based view (RBV), which states that human capital is a crucial asset for organizations to achieve their objectives. By following a structured recruitment and allocation process, the organization ensures that the right personnel are placed in the right roles, thereby enhancing productivity and organizational effectiveness. The entire process reflects a formalized administrative approach, ensuring transparency, efficiency, and the proper deployment of human resources to meet organizational and social service needs.

LKSA follows the regulations as set by the Ministry of Social Affairs, in addition to the recruitment process for human resources in LKSA Muhammadiyah using the rules determined by Muhammadiyah. The recruitment system organized by private institutions is more about developing internal values within the organization, so according to Teimouri & Jenab (2014). (2014) This method is a new approach to knowing needs based on available resources, besides understanding the values that exist in the organization is known.

This research shows that towards character in the management of LKSA by the Muhammadiyah organization, with the mission of shaping the character of Islamic children, the Muhammadiyah LKSA encourages the improvement of human resources that excel in understanding of religion. (Gunawan & Syamsudin, 2023). LKSA Muhammadiyah is functionally the same as the LKSA organized by the government, which focuses on serving children who are abandoned and do not get the needs and protection of the family according to Luh Putu Maitra Ag. (Luh Putu Maitra Agastya et al., 2024)..

In different findings, the recruitment model held by LKSA Muhammadiyah is through a proposal to the central organization in charge of social issues. The Social Welfare Development Assembly as the parent organization in charge of social issues in the Muhammadiyah organization, the function of this organization in LKSA is to carry out the process of HR development and recruitment. In terms of fulfilling human resources, Muhammadiyah business charities including LKSA do not have the authority to recruit employees directly but can only propose human resource needs with certain criteria to the Founding Muhammadiyah Branch Leadership.

Of the four LKSA owned by Muhammadiyah, there are similarities in the recruitment process; the process is based on the needs of the LKSA and the conditions of the LKSA. However, the recruitment process at Taman Harapan LKSA is based on proposals submitted to the Muhammadiyah organizational leadership for consideration. The process of fulfilling our human resources analyzes the needs of LKSA management and later the final results will be proposed to the Muhammadiyah branch leadership for decision making.

Because the Muhammadiyah child social welfare institution is based on a religious organization, it is the main refuge for professionals in carrying out childcare pattern activities. Thus, every activity of the Muhammadiyah child social welfare institution is covered by a sense of safety, security, order, inner and outer peace, and confidence. Faller et al. (2010) organizations in providing social services are based on a commitment to the problems they are concerned about. Muhammadiyah in the history of its establishment has a long commitment to supporting *orphans* and the *poor*. (Jayaratne & Faller, 2009) referred to as the difference between private and public commitment in providing social services to children. In addition, as a large organization, Muhammadiyah and LKSA have a community that is interconnected to provide support in providing human resources in it, by McBeath et al. (2012) which is referred to as the difference between private and public agencies in providing services to children.

The findings further elaborate on the differences in the selection processes undertaken by Muhammadiyah LKSA and the government in encouraging services in child welfare institutions referred to as private and public (McBeath et al., 2012)..

Table 1 Recruitment system of child welfare agencies

Government	Muhammadiyah
Determination of time and cost	Analyzing job requirements
Establishment of selection and qualification procedures	Determination of time and cost
Disseminate human resources recruitment information	Usually recruit interns
Stages of the interview	Usually receiving human resources comes from regeneration
Human resources recruitment	Usually receiving human resources comes from relationships

Source: processed from research results

Table 1, a comparison between the usual practices in human resource management between the government and Muhammadiyah, shows that the difference is in the procedures they apply. First, the government tends to focus more on determining the time and cost of the recruitment process, while Muhammadiyah LKSA thoroughly analyzes the position's needs before determining the appropriate selection procedures and qualifications. Second, the government often sets selection procedures and qualifications before disseminating human resource recruitment information. Muhammadiyah prioritizes the dissemination of recruitment information before determining the appropriate selection procedures. Third, the government tends to conduct interviews as the final stage of selection, while Muhammadiyah is more likely to receive human resources from existing regeneration programs. In addition, Muhammadiyah receives human resources through existing relationships.

Auerbach et al. (2010) found that workers in children's social welfare institutions are generally dissatisfied with the services they provide due to a salary system that is considered inappropriate, even though they provide more optimal services. In the findings of this study there are differences, LKSA Muhammadiyah is driven by religious commitment for workers in it so that salary considerations are not a determining factor for workers in LKSA Muhammadiyah. The strength of Muhammadiyah is that apart from the social aspect, it is strong in doctrine in the religious aspect, meaning that it is not seen from the salary alone, meaning that there are religious values that we get such as sincere work and worship value.

The view of Auerbach et al, (2010) aligns with Muhammadiyah's commitment to social issues in society. Fu et al. (2020) according to the faith base commitment encourages the provision of social services that are cross services from derivative organizations that intersect within Muhammadiyah in this case study. Muhammadiyah's own perspective is a volunteer movement (Anwari et al., 2023; Baidhawiy, 2015) with attention to other social issues such as poverty and natural disasters (Qodir et al., 2023; Baidhawiy, 2015). (Qodir et al., 2022)

4.2. Recruitment system through regeneration of Muhammadiyah institutions

According to Rajbangshi et al, (2017) According to Rajbangshi et al. (2017), retaining the workforce has such a big challenge. As Zhao, (2021) assesses that the regeneration system in China to reduce errors, improve efficiency, and competence of government human resources. Indeed, regeneration provides opportunities for child social welfare agencies to fully manage and optimize human resources through organized recruitment channels. In the *scholars'* findings, the regeneration system in Muhammadiyah child social welfare institutions shows a positive impact on better governance. They utilize the presence of Muhammadiyah cadres to fill strategic positions, which in turn improves the image of Muhammadiyah child social welfare institutions, competent resources, and employment opportunities.

The relationship system develops into an optimal recruitment system to find professionals, through *social networks*, the number of associative ties, and the involvement of faith-based organizations have a strong relationship with the recruitment system. (Paik & Navarre-Jackson, 2010).. Meanwhile, the relationship system has also found some differences in the way the western world views this relationship-based recruitment system (Fernandez & Rubineau, 2010). (Fernandez & Rubineau, 2019).. This research shows that in the relationship system at the Muhammadiyah Child Social Welfare Institution, more staff come from Muhammadiyah members than non-members due to similar values and views. Muhammadiyah children's social welfare institutions use internship and volunteer systems in recruiting professionals, they provide open access to information to undergraduate students to develop knowledge at Muhammadiyah children's social welfare institutions. Efron & Mackey, (2023) assessed that internship and volunteer recruitment procedures are very efficient and effective in assessing a diverse and qualified group of applicants. Meanwhile, Muhammadiyah children's social welfare institutions in recruiting through the internship and volunteer system, ensure that Muhammadiyah values and ideology can be well maintained, and aspects of understanding of Islam.

4.3. Child Welfare Institution Performance, LKSA HR Management

In some views, competence is seen as the main instrument to drive service quality, Bunger et al, (2014) (2014) argued that child social welfare institutions generally build partnerships to show that they have the ability to provide superior services. The above idea is in line with the view of Carnochan et al, (2013) (2013) that private institutions generally prioritize performance to obtain funding coverage to carry out their mission. Knowledge is an important competency, especially related to knowledge in terms of dealing with children, because we are here focusing on children from zero years old to school age, workers must have skills, especially in the tasks they are responsible for, even though they are not yet skilled, but these skills can be developed.

The recruitment process carried out by LKSA through religious organizations contributes especially in increasing the number of human resources, besides this approach is based on desire and volunteerism, however, LKSA sets standards for accepting workers. Paik & Navarre-Jackson (2010) the form of volunteerism initiated by religious organizations encourages joining them, therefore to encourage the improvement of the quality of human resources, according to Hargie, (2021) it is necessary to provide training to improve service

performance. Other findings show that the recruitment system carried out by children's social welfare institutions uses a system where the principle is used by selecting organizations that intersect with Muhammadiyah as the parent organization. Recruitment by targeting members of the Muhammadiyah organization, secondly we also provide information openly about recruitment after conducting internal recruitment and from internal no one is interested.

As a volunteer movement, LKSA also recruits students based on their interest in the issue. Gunawardena & Stich (2021) This method is very helpful for LKSA to carry out human resource management due to limitations and a large number of children. To maintain performance, the number of workers in the LKSA is increased so that the distribution of work is evenly distributed. (Stredwick, 2013). In addition, the way LKSA is promoted by Muhammadiyah applies moral values and habits in the perspective of Islamic organizations. According to Khoirurroji'in et al. (2021) this way as character education applied to children who are cared for, in the same view Gunawan & Syamsudin (2023) assume that LKSA that spearheads religious values aims to form good student character. Attitude competence is a concern with regard to attitude in daily life, receiving guests, among fellow human resources and to children, meaning that attitudes must also be good, besides that understanding of religion is another important aspect.

The competence prioritized by LKSA *Kuncup Harapan* is an understanding of religion and personality which is the benchmark, besides that LKSA *Kuncup Harapan* assesses that with this ability, workers can be professional in carrying out their duties and functions. By Soelton et al. (2023) call it the relationship between culture in the organization, so that the way LKSA applies attitude in daily life as part of the culture in providing services. Religious organizational factors become a pattern that influences so that habits and attitudes become the main part in assessing service performance, Dormer (2011) referred to as a culture that is influenced by the organization itself.

According to O'Leary et al. (2020) the way religion brings its perspective to managing LKSA by increasing understanding of the religion adhered to, therefore human resources that are taxed in LKSA are those who have deep knowledge to achieve these goals. That way in carrying out their duties and responsibilities, the rights of children are fulfilled, as a child welfare agency (Dormer, 2011). (Dormer, 2011) assesses the need to focus on output so that services in LKSA instill good input, besides that the quality of human resources affects the LKSA service itself.

4.4. Improved services of Muhammadiyah children's social welfare institutions

Soelton et al. (2023) Organizational commitment is the basis for providing quality services, as explained in the previous findings section that LKSA Muhammadiyah has a commitment to social problems, one of which is child welfare. The form of commitment is realized in providing qualified services. Muhammadiyah children's social welfare institutions have standard childcare services that are formed into three approaches to care programs, namely; family compensation, family care, and a place to stay for abandoned children. In addition, the concept of care is based on how to educate and teach foster children applied by LKSA referring to the perspective of Islamic teachings. This research underlines that the form of parenting patterns is carried out by workers in the LKSA by Their ability to provide care, but the issues are issues about childcare, conduct training for human resources and collaborate with other organizations to provide a new understanding of the services they are responsible for, in addition we also supervise the services provided.

The organization (LKSA Bayi Sehat) appears committed to improving service delivery through human resource training, collaboration with external organizations, and supervision of services. By engaging in continuous training and partnerships, the organization aims to enhance its caregivers' skills and create a more effective childcare

system. However, the mention of issues suggests potential gaps in service quality, resource availability, or operational efficiency that require attention. Ensuring proper supervision further highlights a commitment to maintaining service standards and accountability.

The findings align with Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979), which emphasizes that a child's development is influenced by multiple environmental factors, including direct caregivers, institutions, and external organizations. By improving human resource capabilities and fostering collaboration, the organization strengthens both the microsystem (direct care environment) and mesosystem (interaction between caregivers and supporting institutions). Additionally, Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978) suggests that learning and development occur through social interactions and shared knowledge. The organization's focus on training and collaboration reflects this theory, as it promotes a culture of continuous learning among caregivers and stakeholders to improve childcare services.

Rohman et al. (2022) The steps taken by LKSA Bayi Sehat as an effort to improve child welfare, through appropriate parenting patterns by providing training for workers at LKSA, in addition to avoiding forms of error in services, the leadership provides direction on the tasks to be carried out. This method is seen as a step to improve services to increase children's trust in caregivers in LKSA. O'Leary et al. (2020) assessed that services like this should bring valuable experiences for children so that they can interact well and increase scientific understanding, especially of religion.

In addition, a linear policy is needed to support the program of the LKSA institution itself, Tilbury (2004) The right policy can encourage the improvement of services to children. This step was also taken by Muhammadiyah to design a model of care through religious education and policies for the development of human resources in it. In the interview findings indicate that LKSA Muhammadiyah conducts good management by evaluating the institution every week with the leadership and managers.

According to Molnar et al, (2020) good management of child social welfare institutions affects service output, the Muhammadiyah LKSA in the findings of this study has a management design with tiered supervision and has a curriculum, this is based on an educational model that is incorporated in the management of child social welfare institutions, so that Muhammadiyah as a religious organization is seen as an institution that can provide social services, Collins-Camargo et al., (2011) assessed that the main factor is the professional management of LKSA and has committed values in it. (Aarons et al., 2012; Collins-Camargo et al., 2014; McBeath et al., 2012).

In addition to the supervision mechanism applied to LKSA Darul Ilmi, to improve the quality of services, LKSA Kuncup Harapan also takes the same steps by providing opportunities for volunteers to join and be involved in community social movements, LKSA Kuncup Harapan provides the same opportunities but through an evaluation process to measure the quality of the resulting performance. The evaluation and decision-making mechanism is based on an informal process that has been running, even though the results are taken into consideration by the leadership of the organization and the structure above it.

As some recent research underlines, LKSA has competencies that should be seen as a key part of providing services for children by professionals (Korpinen & Pösö, 2020). (Korpinen & Pösö, 2020).. Soelton et al. (2023) assessed that private institutions prefer non-formal mechanisms to manage but with strong commitments, this finding shows that there is a commitment to religious values which is a major factor in it. Institutionally, LKSA Muhammadiyah is an establish organization through good institutional management in building and educating character for children. (Indarwati & Sahrul, 2024; Putri & Sahrul, 2021; Sahrul et al., 2022)..

LKSA services for children have been determined by the Muhammadiyah organizational leadership, so that LKSA as a derivative organization can follow the predetermined instructions. This method according to Göçmen, (2013) according to the FBO perspective used, in line with the view that Soelton et al. (2023) There are strong relationships in the management of child social welfare institutions, such as culture and leadership. In principle, in Darul Ilmi, the steps that must be taken are to follow the rules of the Muhammadiyah association, the association has a culture and authority in recruiting. Muhammadiyah conducts various processes in determining business charities because Muhammadiyah is the founder of this institution.

Furthermore, this study classifies the types of services provided by Muhammadiyah LKSA; from four Muhammadiyah LKSA, we categorize the patterns of care and services provided. Table 2 illustrates the support services that Muhammadiyah's child social welfare institutions offer to vulnerable families, with the aim of fulfilling their basic rights and providing care. This is a priority model that must be followed to prevent children from being separated from their families. Table 2: Muhammadiyah children's social welfare institutions provide excellent child care patterns by prioritizing the fulfillment of children's basic needs such as food, clothing, health, shelter, and education, and providing useful activities such as recreation.

Table 2. Childcare Patterns of LKSA Muhammadiyah

Parenting Patterns	Output
Residential facilities	Every child can feel comfortable in the Muhammadiyah child welfare institution.
Customized clothing facilities	There is a clear insight into appearance for foster children
Provision of school uniforms	Children are able to perform confidently
Food facilities	In accordance with the 4 healthy 5 perfect standard. Children are not bored with the existing menu. With different menus, children's appetite for food increases. Making children independent and guaranteed health.
Health facilities	Children's health is always maintained and controlled
School facilities	The level of education is a service that must be received by every child so that they are able to feel the feasibility of a guaranteed education.
Recreation	Promotes a calm atmosphere in children

Source: processed from research results

The management pattern of LKSA Muhammadiyah provides services by providing facilities to support the growth and development of children. Huggins-Hoyt et al, (2019) Private agencies have good performance in handling children's social welfare problems, in this case analysis, the Muhammadiyah LKSA of the four has a curriculum to educate children, but the recruitment pattern is through a more differentiated approach, some choose to use volunteers or go through the recruitment process by Muhammadiyah. Through the designed mechanism, LKSA managers can measure the resulting performance (Samples et al., 2013). (Samples et al., 2013) In addition, the management category in it because it involves the main Muhammadiyah structure so that supervision and management are balanced, this is in line with the view that the quality of LKSA will be influenced by both (Singh Dubey et al., 2013). (Singh Dubey et al., 2022; Stredwick, 2013)..

Hargie, (2021) training programs are mandatory to encourage services in LKSA. LKSA conducts evaluations in three and six months to improve the skills of workers and improve services, besides that children are an important part of it to find out the services that have been provided by workers. Qodir et al. (2022) The social and religious movement promoted by the Muhammadiyah LKSA shows the consistent management of the LKSA on social issues and runs continuously, this way is seen by Baidhawiy (2015). (2015) as part of problem solving. Finally, we underline that there are patterns of LKSA management by both religious and government institutions where the character of both is shown through recruitment patterns, commitment to social issues, financing patterns and LKSA management.

5. CONCLUSION AND LIMITATION

The study of child social welfare in this study categorizes several functions of LKSA and its management. First, we assess that the Muhammadiyah child welfare institution is organized with religious commitment by looking at social problems in the community, so that the Muhammadiyah LKSA has a mission to educate and care for children who need social welfare services. Second, the management of LKSA Muhammadiyah is based on the policies of the parent organization, so that the recruitment process and human resource development are carried out following the policies of the parent organization. To support the quality of services, LKSA conducts an evaluation mechanism which is held in three and six months to determine the quality of services provided by workers.

The findings classify the functions of public and private LKSA managed by the state and Muhammadiyah, where both have different management and service mechanisms. In addition, Muhammadiyah LKSA services also emphasize religious character education so that children grow up in a good environment. Through Muhammadiyah values, it is the power that moves the spirit to carry out charitable activities in social services, increase the diligence of worship, and develop skilled and competent human resources. Practical findings, Muhammadiyah has an Islamic life guideline for everyone who works in Muhammadiyah children's social welfare institutions to do something good that is realized from activities such as the study of the Koran, and Hadith, so that human resources in Muhammadiyah child welfare institutions work with competence, capacity, and provide the best service in childcare.

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Declaration of interest statement

No potential conflict

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